

INDEPENDENCE OF TRANSPORT NETWORKS ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN THE ECONOMY AND ITS IMPACT ON DEVELOPMENT.

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Abstract. At present, all spheres of our country are developing. Along with them, the country's transport system has developed more rapidly than before, reaching a level where it can compete directly with a number of foreign countries. Its importance in the country's economy is very high. Although its role in export, import, international trade, economic relations is immeasurable, but its harmful substances released into the environment are causing damage to the environment. This article discusses in detail the development system of transport and its impact on the environment, its study and solutions.

Keywords. Transport, Uzbekistan, railway, road transport, ecology, Fergana valley, export, import.

The role and importance of transport in the socio-economic development of any region and raising the standard of living of the population is incomparable. Transport provides production links between industry and agriculture, exchange of products between different regions of the country, and its foreign trade. Before the development of new territories, transport routes will be transferred to them. The life of modern cities cannot be imagined without transport. The defense value of transport is also very great. Transport is one of the important branches of material production. Its level of development has a direct impact on the country's economy, location and development of production forces. The Republic of Uzbekistan was established as an independent state on September 1, 1991. The area is 448.9 thousand km². Administratively, it consists of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, 12 regions and the city of Tashkent. Uzbekistan has a unique position on the world community and political map. Our country is located almost in the heart of Central Asia. It does not have direct access to the sea. Due to this, in the transport system, air, pipeline, car, railway transport is often used for conducting foreign trade relations and developing relations with other countries. Transport provides production links between industry and agriculture, and exchange of products between different regions. Transport types are usually used to develop new areas. Currently, the country cannot be imagined without transport. Transport

is also of great importance in the defense system. It is well known from history that trade, science, and crafts have reached high levels in the areas where the Great Silk Road passed. After this road lost its importance, the geopolitical position of the region changed a lot. As a result, modern Uzbekistan has become a landlocked country farthest from seaports. Today, the shortest railway of the republic to the Black Sea, the Baltic Sea, the Sea of Japan, and the North Sea is about 3,000 km long. This is a long way that passes through the territory of several countries, which complicates the economic relations of Uzbekistan, increases the cost of transportation and makes products uncompetitive. Regional organization and development of transport in the conditions of market relations is one of the main tasks of our government.

The main part.

The step-by-step development of transport in Uzbekistan is detailed below.

Railways occupy a leading and important place among the types of transport available in Uzbekistan. The importance of this type of transport in foreign economic relations of countries, especially in export and import relations, is incomparable. Another advantage of rail transport over other modes of transport is that it is less harmful to the environment, it has a very high capacity for carrying goods and passengers, it is not affected by the vagaries of the weather and regularly will be in motion. In this way, it is very different from automobile and especially air transport. Railway transport plays an important role, especially in inter-regional economic relations. Railway construction in Uzbekistan began in 1888. The Krasnovodsk-Chorjoi railway was continued from the station to Samarkand. From 1890, it was delivered from Tashkent to Andijan. In 1905, a railway was launched between Orenburg and Tashkent. Despite economic difficulties, the government of the republic attached great importance to the restoration of damaged railways and the construction of new roads. In 1934, the opening of the Turkestan highway was very important in the economic development of the republic. Angren railway was built and put into operation in the years before independence. In 1952-1956, with the construction of the Chorjoi-Kungirov railway, lower Amudarya was connected with other regions of Uzbekistan in the former union. In 1962, the Navoi Uchkuduk railway was completed and put into operation. Syrdaryo-Jizzakh was connected with Samarkand-Karshi at a short distance. In 1972, the Denov railway was built through Kungirov-Ustyurt. Now, Central Asia is connected to Europe by a two-way railway.

Road transport is developing rapidly in Uzbekistan. This is mainly transport

The Republic plays an important role in the transportation of interregional and inter-economy goods. In recent years, its importance in the transportation of economic goods of the Commonwealth of Nations and other international countries is increasing. Car transport, especially in 1926, began to transport passengers using regular buses in the republic (the first intercity bus service was launched in 1906 on the Fergana-Margilan route). Since then, the number and quality of passenger buses has increased significantly. It is the main means of transport in desert, hilly and mountainous areas where there is no railway. Several concrete roads - Tashkent-Almaliq road, Greater Uzbekistan tract, Fergana public road, Zarafshan and Karakalpakstan tarkts and other roads were built. Currently, about 70 bus and taxi motor sheds have been built in the Republic, they are equipped with modern equipment.

Air transport. The history of the republic's air transport-civil aviation began in the 1920s. On May 20, 1924, the first passenger flight was carried out on the Tashkent-Avliyota (Jhambul)-Pishpek (Bishkek)-Almaota route, which was 800 km long. In the same year, the Kogon-Oktokai-Darganota-Khiva and Bukhara-Termiz-Doshanbe air routes with a length of 450 km were opened. In 1924, a total of 1,000 passengers, 200 kg of mail, and 5 tons of cargo were transported by air transport. Since 1930, planes have been regularly flying on the Tashkent-Moscow route. At the same time, the construction of airports was also started. First, in 1932 in Tashkent, in 1939 in Nukus and Urganch, in 1940 in Termiz, in 1941 in Namangan, airports were built and put into operation.

Pipeline transport. If we look at the history, the first oil in Uzbekistan we see that the pipeline was put into operation in 1908. In the same year, a 20 km long pipeline was laid from Chimyon oil field to Altiariq oil refinery. Later, the discovery of new oil and gas fields in the country became the basis for the development of pipeline transport. Now there is a total of 228.5 km from the oil fields to the Fergana and Altiariq oil refineries alone.

Water transport. In 1950, the Termiz river port was established in the middle reaches of Amudarya in Surkhandarya region. In 1952, a ship repair plant was built in Khojaly. In the lower part of the Amudarya, Sharlavuk, Tortkol, Beruniy, Karatov, Khojayli harbors (wharves) were built on the banks of the river in different years.

Transportation is one of the main sources of air pollution. Its environmental impact is as follows. Environmental problems related to the impact of various transport objects on the environment are determined by the amount of emissions of toxic substances by engines, as well as the pollution of water bodies. Solid waste and noise pollution contribute to the negative impact. In addition, it is primarily the car transport that pollutes the environment and

uses energy sources. The negative impact of rail vehicles is an order of magnitude lower. Pollution of air, sea and inland water transport will be reduced.

Social and economic development of any region and the life of the population the role and essence of transport in raising the level of education is incomparable. Transport provides production links between industry and agriculture, exchange of products between different regions of the country, and its foreign trade. Before the development of new territories, transport routes will be transferred to them. The life of modern cities cannot be imagined without transport.

As a result of the work carried out in the field of transport in Uzbekistan, new settlements, cities, industrial enterprises, transport hubs are created, the image of the regions changes, transit road and railway transport brings a certain benefit to the economy. It should be noted that "the road of a developed country will not be good, on the contrary, a country with a good road will be developed" and it is not difficult to understand that one of the bases determining the country's socio-economic development is transport systems.

In fact, the economic reforms implemented in the republic are aimed at improving the transport network, creating legal bases for the operation of national air and railway companies in market conditions, and ensuring their coordination with the international communication system. Ferghana Economic Region, located in the eastern part of the republic, in a "closed" state, has better transport and geographical conditions than other regions of the republic..

Discussion.

The environmental impact of motor transport burns a large amount of petroleum products, cars harm the environment (primarily the atmosphere) and human health. The air is saturated with oxygen, saturated with harmful substances of exhaust gases, the amount of dust accumulated in the atmosphere and collected on the surface of various substrates increases. The automobile transport complex is a powerful source of environmental pollution. 89 percent of the 35 million tons of harmful waste is the waste of automobile transport and road construction enterprises. Transport is of great importance in the pollution of water bodies. In addition, traffic is one of the main sources of noise in cities and contributes greatly to thermal pollution of the environment. In addition, 200 km³ of wastewater containing pathogenic microorganisms enter passenger cars every kilometer of road per year. , as well as up to 12 tons of dry garbage.

According to the data, road transport takes the leading place in terms of damage to the environment, it is the main source of air pollution. It accounts for more

than 90% of air pollution, a little over 50% of noise impact, and 65-68% of climate impact.

Noise and air pollution from moving trains have a negative impact on human health and generally affect the quality of life of the population.

Results.

In order to combat the deterioration of the environment, it is necessary to develop inexpensive environmentally safe criteria and environmentally friendly technologies, and most importantly, to ensure public participation in environmental activities.

After all, it is impossible to imagine solving global environmental problems without public participation. The first steps to involve the general public in environmental protection should be:

- eliminating the information vacuum, providing the population with the necessary environmental information provide. Here, the active position of mass media, journalists and bloggers, who are the link between the government and the population, is important;
- all objects that affect the environment in one way or another and introduction of the mechanism of expert supervision of constructions and public discussion;
- introduction of a mechanism of public control over the spending of budget funds allocated for nature protection, as well as the distribution and spending of foreign investments;
- development of environmental information transmission, storage and processing systems.

Literature analysis.

An analysis of the literature written on this situation showed that we will consider this in the example of the Fergana Valley. The importance and role of vehicles in the economy of Fergana Valley is increasing day by day. It is an integral part of efforts to further develop foreign economic relations. It can be seen that the development of foreign economic relations of the valley is directly dependent on the fact that the existing industrial enterprises in the region are provided with transport infrastructure and modern types of transport. Therefore, in order to further develop foreign economic relations in the future, it is necessary to establish rail, road and air transport to distant foreign countries and make full use of the available opportunities.

Conclusion.

In short, transportation allows for the deepening of the geographical division of labor both throughout the country and around the world by transporting cargo

and passengers. It plays an important role in the development of cultural, political and economic relations with other countries. Transport types are usually grouped according to the type of cargo they carry, how much they carry, and the speed of movement, but vehicles with a large volume have a large impact on the environment.

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